

CYCLOPES - Fighting Cybercrime – Law Enforcement Practitioners’ Network

Deliverable 5.3

2nd Annual CYCLOPES Community Building Report

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1. Summary

One of the main goals of the CYCLOPES project is to build, strengthen and maintain links with initiatives, actions, and projects relevant to CYCLOPES, learning and developing from the collective efforts, where possible. Continuing from the foundation laid in the 1st Annual CYCLOPES Community Building Report (D5.2), the CYCLOPES consortium went from the phase of being visible and open to the phase where a more active approach towards community building has been central. The partners of the CYCLOPES consortium have used their available means in order to reach end users from LEAs, academia and industry.

This report D5.3 “2nd Annual CYCLOPES Community Building Report” describes the main results achieved from May 2022 to April 2023.

2. Introduction

A broad and active community is essential in building an open network for European experienced practitioners’ working in the field of fighting cybercrime. However, there are already many institutions, networks and other initiatives focused on these domains that are relevant for the CYCLOPES project.

Aside from internal LEA community, CYCLOPES form a bridge between the project and: 1) EU and international organisations, such as EC, EC3, Europol’s Innovation Hub, Interpol, ENISA, etc. 2) Networks of practitioners, especially ENLETS, ENFSI, i-LEAD, iLeaNet, EU-HYBNET and i-ProcureNet 3) Networks and relevant stakeholders related to cybersecurity 4) Research, Industry, Ethical and Social societies and organisations.

In the first year of the project implementation, the methodology was developed as a starting point for establishing relations with the relevant stakeholders. The CYCLOPES Community Building Framework and Governance model (D5.1) defined the methodology, by which over the course of this 5 year project, all members of the CYCLOPES community work together to reach the goals, ambition and granted objectives of the project.

3. Overview of main achievements: 2nd year (May 2022 – April 2023)

During the first year, most actions have evolved around gaining awareness and visibility; in the second year, focused on the implementation, the team invited and motivated practitioners and other stakeholders to have a more practical hands-on experience with the CYCLOPES activities. The project builds, strengthens and maintains links with the following key stakeholders and networks whose work is conducted in the areas relevant to CYCLOPES:

- European Commission, DG HOME
- European Union Agency for Criminal Justice Cooperation (EJCN),
- European Anti-Cybercrime Technology Development Association (EACTDA),
- European Cybercrime Training and Education Group (ECTEG),
- European Network of Forensic Science Institutes (ENFSI),
- European Network of Law Enforcement Technology Services (ENLETS),
- EUROPOL Innovation Lab.

Figure 1 Cooperation with other relevant stakeholders

The cooperation with the above networks and stakeholders is foreseen through exchanging information about the ongoing and planned activities, particularly workshops, surveys/questionnaires, conferences, etc. The exchange of selected reports and other project outcomes relevant for both parties, and the synchronisation of conducted actions, should help avoid duplicating and overlapping work.

3.1. Key stakeholders

The project has ongoing communication and exchange of information about events and ongoing activities with the following key stakeholders:

- a. European Commission, DG HOME (D.4. Security in the digital age). The Commission's Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs is responsible for the EU's internal security policy, which is a component of the new Security Union Strategy 2020-2025. The aim is to build a safer Europe by fighting terrorism and organised crime, by promoting police cooperation and by preparing to swiftly respond to emerging crises. DG HOME actions in these areas include stricter rules against illicit trafficking of firearms and on trafficking in human beings, as well as revision of legislation on combating child sexual abuse, sexual exploitation and child pornography.¹
- b. European Union Agency for Criminal Justice Cooperation (EJCN). EJCN was established to foster contacts between practitioners specialised in countering the challenges posed by cybercrime, cyber-enabled crime and investigations in cyberspace, and to increase the efficiency of investigations and prosecutions. The EJCN facilitates and enhances cooperation between competent judicial authorities by enabling the exchange of expertise, best practice and other relevant knowledge regarding the investigation and prosecution of cybercrime.²
- c. European Anti-Cybercrime Technology Development Association (EACTDA). The purpose of the Association is the development of technological solutions for European

¹ https://commission.europa.eu/about-european-commission/departments-and-executive-agencies/migration-and-home-affairs_en

² <https://www.eurojust.europa.eu/>

Law Enforcement Agencies and Forensic Laboratories to use them in their fight against crime.³

- d. European Cybercrime Training and Education Group (ECTEG). ECTEG is composed of European Union and European Economic Area Member States law enforcement agencies, international bodies, academia, private industry and experts. The primary aim of the working group is to provide experience and knowledge to further enhance the coordination of cybercrime training, by identifying opportunities to build the capacity of countries to combat cybercrime through the development and delivery of a robust and enduring training programme.⁴
- e. European Network of Forensic Science Institutes (ENFSI). ENFSI was founded with the purpose of improving the mutual exchange of information in the field of forensic science. This, as well as improving the quality of forensic science delivery in Europe have become the main issues of the network. Besides the general work in the fields of quality and competence management, research and development and education and training, different forensic expertizes are dealt with by 17 different Expert Working Groups.⁵
- f. European Network of Law Enforcement Technology Services (ENLETS). ENLETS brings together 29 members from across Europe to address and action shared priorities. ENLETS works by sharing best practices on a broad level, engaging on mutual priorities and stimulating future projects that can help fill the gaps and known issues facing law enforcement. The environment promotes collaboration and fosters a supportive network, working to help each other through current challenges.⁶
- g. EUROPOL Innovation Lab. The Lab aims to identify, promote and develop concrete innovative solutions in support of the EU Member States' operational work. These will help investigators and analysts to make the most of the opportunities offered by new technologies to avoid duplication of work, create synergies and pool resources.⁷

Moreover, in the third year of the project implementation, a cooperation also with INTERPOL and CEPOL will be initiated.

3.2. CYCLOPES Community Members

One of CYCLOPES' key goals is to build and maintain an innovation-driven network of European law enforcement agencies and experts specialised in combating cybercrime. A different techniques and platforms are commonly used to engage with the CYCLOPES communities - some of them are designed specifically to share information, while others aim to successfully involve practitioners, industry and researchers in relevant activities'.

It is possible to join CYCLOPES Community after signing up on <https://cyclopes-project.eu>, (via click on JOIN US button). This page provides a snapshot of the project and what members can expect from supporting the initiative. At the beginning of the project, CYCLOPES created the list of Community Members, which is stored on the project repository and increase during

³ <https://www.eactda.eu/index.html>

⁴ <https://www.ecteg.eu/>

⁵ <https://enfsi.eu/>

⁶ <https://enlets.eu/>

⁷ <https://www.europol.europa.eu/operations-services-and-innovation/innovation-lab>

the course of the project. There is currently around 200 practitioners involved, who work in the field of fighting cybercrime.

Figure 2 CYCLOPES network geographical regions

Specific members of the CYCLOPES Community are involved in the project activities through participation in the practitioners' workshops, annual dissemination workshops, webinars and other relevant activities. Moreover, CYCLOPES is in continuous contact with all Community members, to synchronise works, helping to define the CYCLOPES priority topics for the following years.

3.3. Cooperation with research and industry

Gathering information about the latest technologies and solutions to fight cybercrime is a critical part of CYCLOPES project. Rather than only provide LEAs written recommendations, CYCLOPES organise complementary actions to showcase the technologies and solutions that can assist LEAs to counter specific crimes. These events and gatherings include a mixture of demonstrations, presentations and novel 'Joint Live Exercises (JLE)' that provides LEAs with an opportunity to get 'hands on' with the technologies – testing and evaluating them directly with the providers.

On 18th – 20th April 2023 around 20 law enforcement practitioners from across Europe met in Zagreb in the second edition of the Joint Live Exercises to test and interact with leading European solutions that support LEAs in tackling the rising challenges of crimes connected with various crypto assets. From the high-level list of gaps and needs, the project prepared a concept note introducing the event and invited 5 technology providers to introduce their work, demonstrate its use, and allow the LEAs to get hands-on with the technology and try its functions.

The sessions give everyone a unique chance to interact and exchange useful guidance on how both LEAs and technology providers can adjust to distil greater value that can help prevent and deal with criminal activities.

3.4. ENLETS Messenger Service (EMS)

Part of the community building activities is focused on cooperation with use of communication and collaboration platforms developed or used in other networks. This provides an ideal opportunity to exploit the efforts of these initiatives, and spend time on establishing links and building relations, rather than the considerable time and resources required to develop such communication channels.

Therefore, the CYCLOPES Consortium decided that a new communication platform is not needed, based upon previous experiences in other projects. ENLETS has offered a dedicated space for CYCLOPES Community on their ENLETS Messenger Service (EMS), where practitioners can chat, collaborate on work-related topics and establish relations. This solution provides a safe, encrypted chat experience through a dedicated mobile application and web browser service.

CYCLOPES currently use a dedicated channel for internal communication as well as ENLETS 'general' channel for sharing information about the upcoming events and relevant outcomes.

4. Upcoming and planned community building activities

In the coming months of the implementation, the project will continue collaboration with key stakeholders as well as research projects and other initiatives in the area of fighting cybercrime. To effectively manage community building, the following steps are being implemented:

Figure 3 Community building plan

To achieve the results, a dedicated electronic template has been created to collect all relevant projects and initiatives cybercrime that might be of interest to the CYCLOPES project as well as establish connections. This process will be flexible and adapted to the current needs.

In addition, one of the future goal of the CYCLOPES project is to establish a stronger bridge between practitioners, academia and industry to monitor how research and innovation can address the requirements, gaps and challenges identified by practitioners during the workshops. The next Dissemination Event and online webinar are already planned in June 2023.

5. Conclusion

This document described how the building of CYCLOPES Community is managed and summarised the results achieved in the period from November 2022 to April 2023. This report may also have informative value for other stakeholders to build greater awareness of the planned CYCLOPES activities and foster synergies.

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